

ACTION OF BROMINE ON OXYMETHYLENE CYCLOHEXANONE : FORMATION
OF α -BROMO- β -KETO-ALDEHYDE (1-CYCLOHEXANONE-2-BROMO-2-
ALDEHYDE)

BY A. S. MEHTA, R. KAUSHAL AND N. S. DESHPANDE

By the action of bromine on oxymethylene-cyclohexanone α -bromo- β -ketoaldehyde (1-cyclohexanone-2-bromo-2-aldehyde) has been formed. Evidence is advanced in favour of Kurt Meyer's hypothesis of alcoholic bromine addition for the estimation of keto-enolic mixtures.

In a keto-enolic equilibrium mixture a chemical method for the estimation of enols is suggested by Meyer (*Annalen*, 1911, 380, 212; *Ber.*, 1911, 44, 2718; 1912, 45, 2843). It consists in adding alcoholic solution of bromine to the mixture. The enol rapidly absorbs bromine forming an unstable dibromide which immediately gives off hydrobromic acid and produces a bromoketone. From the amount of bromine absorbed, the quantity of the enol in the mixture is found out as the keto form does not absorb bromine. Thus in the case of acetoacetic ester the reactions are as follows :

The above cannot be a method for the preparation of bromoacetoacetic ester (I) as according to Meyer himself the enol is only 7% in the ordinary acetoacetic ester. Yet bromoacetoacetic ester is prepared by the action of bromine on acetoacetic ester mixed with ice-water (Conrod and Schmidt, *Ber.*, 1896, 29, 1044) and it is not clear whether the mechanism of bromination is in this case the same as assumed by Meyer or it is a mere case of bromination by substitution. If, however, bromine and acetoacetic ester are made to react at 0° in carbon tetrachloride in place of ice-water, γ -bromoacetoacetic ester results. Here obviously, the action of bromine on the ester cannot be on the line suggested by Meyer.

Another keto-enolic system, where halogenation has been studied, is afforded by 1 : 3-diketones (II). Thus by the action of bromine on dibenzoylmethane (II, R=R'=Ph) Neufille and Pechmann (*Ber.*, 1890, 23, 3377) obtained bromodibenzoylmethane (III, R=R'=Ph; X=Br).

It is not clear whether the bromination is effected by addition or by mere substitution. In the case of acetylacetone (II, R=R'=CH₃) no bromo compound is described. Combes (*Compt. rend.*, 1890, 111, 273), however, prepared chloroacetylacetone (III, R=R'=CH₃; X=Cl) by the action of sulphuryl chloride on acetylacetone.

The β -ketoaldehydes (IV) which are really formyl derivatives of a ketone belong to the general class of 1 : 3-dicarbonyl compounds (II) like the β -ketoic esters or the

3-diketones. Claisen has shown that β -ketoaldehydes (IV) exist mostly as their enols of oxymethylene ketones (V).

It is clear that an excellent means of testing Kurt Meyer's hypothesis would be to observe the action of bromine on oxymethylene ketones (V). Some of the oxymethylene ketones are quite unstable and in an attempt to isolate them in pure condition they undergo self-condensation and change into trisubstituted benzenes (Claisen and Stylos, *Ber.*, 1888, 31, 1145). Hence oxymethylene *cyclohexanone* (VI), which cannot undergo self-condensation, was selected for the test (*cf.* also Kaushal, Sovani and Deshapande, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 107).

When pure oxymethylene *cyclohexanone* is dissolved in a mixture of dry ether and carbon tetrachloride and to this at 0° bromine, dissolved in carbon tetrachloride, is gradually added, the latter is rapidly absorbed. A sticky semi-solid substance gradually separates. When the reaction is carried out in dry pure ether only, the quality of the reaction product improves and also the yield. The product is grey and somewhat brown. After the addition of bromine is complete and the reaction mixture is still at 0° and when the hydrobromic acid slowly begins to come out, the mixture is quickly filtered and the grey solid quickly washed with dry ether. The evolution of hydrobromic acid continues and the product is dried on a porous plate in a calcium chloride desiccator. The solid is unstable and cannot be preserved. It can keep under dry ether for sometime but afterwards begins to change into a dark coloured liquid. Purified by washing it has been analysed

and the results of analysis indicate that it is α -bromo- β -ketoaldehyde (VII) formed obviously by the addition of bromine to the enol (VI) followed by loss of hydrobromic acid. At each of the stages (i) absorption of bromine and (ii) loss of hydrobromic acid have been separately observed and as the second stage follows a few minutes after the first, this affords a strong evidence in favour of Kurt Meyer's hypothesis.

That (VII) is an aldehyde readily follows from the observations that it reduces Fehling's solution and with ammoniacal silver nitrate it gives a silver mirror with some precipitate of silver bromide. Similar behaviour is shown by α -bromopropionic aldehyde (Franke, *Annalen*, 1907, 351, 423). The aldehyde (VII) forms a disemicarbazone losing at the same time a molecule of hydrobromic acid which is taken up by the base semicarbazide. The semicarbazone has therefore the structure (X). This semicarbazone (X) differs from the semicarbazone (VIII) of the original oxymethylene cyclohexanone both in its melting point and composition. Moreover, (X) readily absorbs large volumes of bromine water while (VIII) does so only very slowly.

The bromo-aldehyde (VII) also condenses with aniline to form an anil, m.p. 142° containing no bromine. Here also hydrobromic acid seems to have been removed by aniline and the anil formed has the structure (XI). The oxymethylene cyclohexanone, however, forms an anilide (IX) m.p. 169°.

From the above results it seems that by the action of bromine on oxymethylene cyclohexanone, the α -bromo- β -ketoaldehyde (VII) has been synthesised, which is unstable.

EXPERIMENTAL

Oxymethylene cyclohexanone (VI) was prepared by Claisen's method using for one molecule cyclohexanone 1.25 mols. of ethyl formate and 1.25 atoms of sodium wire in dry ether under ice-cooling. On working the sodium compound thus formed, crude oxymethylene cyclohexanone was obtained as orange coloured liquid which passed over as almost colourless liquid at 79°/4 mm. 14 G. cyclohexanone gave 11 g. pure oxymethylene cyclohexanone (cf. Wallach, *Annalen*, 1903, 329, 109). It is volatile in steam and with acids on heating gives highly coloured solution and with ferric chloride produces intense violet colour.

The disemicarbazone (VIII) of oxymethylene cyclohexanone, prepared as usual, separated as white crystalline mass. It was dried and recrystallised from water, m.p. 231° (decomp.). (Found in the material dried at 120° for two hours: N, 34.7. $C_6H_{10}O_2N_2$ requires N, 35.0 per cent.)

The oxymethylene cyclohexanone anilide (IX) was prepared on mixing oxymethylene cyclohexanone and aniline separately dissolved in ether, when heat was evolved and a solid began to separate. It was cooled and allowed to remain for sometime. The yellow compound was filtered, washed, dried and recrystallised from absolute alcohol as long, thick, star-shaped needles, m.p. 169°. (Found: N, 7.2, 6.8. $C_{13}H_{18}ON$ requires N, 6.9 per cent.)

Action of Bromine on Oxymethylene cyclohexanone: Formation of (VII).—Oxymethylene cyclohexanone (1 part) was dissolved in dry ether (3 parts) and the mixture well cooled in ice. Well cooled ether solution of bromine was slowly added in instalments.

On shaking a yellowish grey solid separated which began losing hydrobromic acid. A little more bromine was added until the supernatant liquid acquired a pale yellow colour. It was well shaken and allowed to remain in ice for 5 minutes and then quickly filtered at the pump and washed well with dry ether. It was dried in a calcium chloride desiccator. 2.5 G. oxymethylene cyclohexanone gave 2 g. of the bromo-aldehyde. It could not be crystallised, purified by washing with dry ether it melted at 88-90°. (Found : C, 39.9 ; H, 5.0 ; Br, 39.6. $C_7H_9O_2Br$ requires C, 40.9 ; H, 4.4 ; Br, 39.0 per cent).

The product is unstable and on exposure it changes into a dark coloured liquid. With water, alcohol or other solvents it passes into a dark coloured liquid. It reduces Fehling's solution and ammoniacal silver nitrate.

Action of Semicarbazide on the Bromo-aldehyde (VII) : Formation of the Disemicarbazone (X).—A little of the bromo-aldehyde was added to a solution of semicarbazide hydrochloride and sodium acetate when it went into solution giving a yellow colour. On shaking and scratching the semicarbazone separated as yellowish white solid which was filtered, washed, dried and recrystallised from dilute alcohol and dried at 120°, m.p. 190°. (Found : N, 34.8. $C_9H_{14}O_2N_4$ requires N, 35.3 per cent.) It takes up readily large amounts of bromine water.

Action of Aniline on the Bromo-aldehyde (VII) : Formation of Anil (XI).—To 1 g. of the bromo-aldehyde aniline was added in drops and the whole mixed well. Condensation with aniline took place with evolution of heat. The crude product on crystallisation from alcohol separated as brownish thick prisms melting at 142° and was found to contain no bromine, yield 0.5 g. (Found : N, 7.3. $C_{13}H_{13}ON$ requires N, 7.0 per cent).